

Appendix D Raw data for the 3 test days:

Raw data of test day 1 (21st January, 2024):

Number of test:	Left Elbow (5 shots)	In (%) Left Elbow	Free Throw (10 shots)	In (%) Free Throw	Right Elbow (5 shots)	In (%) Right Elbow
Participant A1						
1	0/5	0.0%	4/10	40.0%	0/5	0.0%
2	3/5	60.0%	6/10	60.0%	3/5	60.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	5/10	50.0%	1/5	20.0%
Participant A2						
1	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	4/5	80.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	5/10	50.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant A3						
1	1/5	20.0%	4/10	40.0%	3/5	60.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	3/5	60.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	4/10	40.0%	3/5	60.0%
Participant B1						
1	1/5	20.0%	7/10	70.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	4/5	80.0%	2/10	20.0%	4/5	80.0%
Participant B2						
1	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	6/10	60.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	0/5	0.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
Participant C1						
1	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	6/10	60.0%	1/5	20.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	6/10	60.0%	3/5	60.0%
Participant C2						
1	1/5	20.0%	6/10	60.0%	3/5	60.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	6/10	60.0%	1/5	20.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant D1						
1	1/5	20.0%	0/10	0.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant E1						
1	0/5	0.0%	1/10	10.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	2/10	20.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%

Data chart 1

Number of test:	3pt Right Wing (5 shots)	In (%) 3pt Right wing	3pt Top of the key (10 shots)	In (%) 3pt Top of the key	3pt Left Wing (5 shots)	In (%) 3pt Left Wing
Participant A1						
1	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
3	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant A2						
1	1/5	20.0%	3/10	30.0%	3/5	60.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	1/10	10.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant A3						
1	0/5	0.0%	2/10	20.0%	0/5	0.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	0/5	0.0%	2/10	20.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant B1						
1	1/5	20.0%	1/10	10.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	3/10	30.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant B2						
1	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant C1						
1	1/5	20.0%	4/10	40.0%	3/5	60.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	6/10	60.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	4/5	80.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant C2						
1	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	5/10	50.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant D1						
1	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant E1						
1	0/5	0.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	1/5	20.0%

Data chart 2

These two data charts are from the first day of testing. They show the nine participants' initial shooting percentages from the six locations, 120 shots in total each participant.

Raw data of test day 2 (day 28 of experiment 18th February, 2024):

C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Number of test:	Left Elbow (5 shots)	In (%) Left Elbow	Free Throw (10 shots)	In (%) Free Throw	Right Elbow (5 shots)	In (%) Right Elbow	3p
Participant A1							
1	0/5	0.0%	4/10	40.0%	0/5	0.0%	
2	3/5	60.0%	6/10	60.0%	3/5	60.0%	
3	1/5	20.0%	5/10	50.0%	1/5	20.0%	
Participant A2							
1	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	4/5	80.0%	
2	0/5	0.0%	5/10	50.0%	2/5	40.0%	
3	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%	
Participant A3							
1	1/5	20.0%	4/10	40.0%	3/5	60.0%	
2	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	3/5	60.0%	
3	2/5	40.0%	4/10	40.0%	3/5	60.0%	
Participant B1							
1	1/5	20.0%	7/10	70.0%	2/5	40.0%	
2	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%	
3	4/5	80.0%	2/10	20.0%	4/5	80.0%	
Participant B2							
1	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%	
2	0/5	0.0%	6/10	60.0%	0/5	0.0%	
3	0/5	0.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%	
Participant C1							
1	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%	
2	1/5	20.0%	6/10	60.0%	1/5	20.0%	
3	1/5	20.0%	6/10	60.0%	3/5	60.0%	
Participant C2							
1	1/5	20.0%	6/10	60.0%	3/5	60.0%	
2	1/5	20.0%	6/10	60.0%	1/5	20.0%	
3	1/5	20.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%	
Participant D1							
1	1/5	20.0%	0/10	0.0%	1/5	20.0%	
2	1/5	20.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%	
3	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%	
Participant E1							
1	0/5	0.0%	1/10	10.0%	1/5	20.0%	
2	0/5	0.0%	2/10	20.0%	0/5	0.0%	
3	1/5	20.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%	

Data chart 3

Number of test:	3pt Right Wing (5 shots)	In (%) 3pt Right Wing	3pt Top of the key (10 shots)	In (%) 3pt Top of the key	3pt Left Wing (5 shots)	In (%) 3pt Left Wing
Participant A1						
1	1/5	20.0%	0/10	0.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	3/5	60.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	3/10	30.0%	3/5	60.0%
Participant A2						
1	1/5	20.0%	0/10	0.0%	2/10	20.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	2/10	20.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	2/10	20.0%
Participant A3						
1	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	1/10	10.0%	1/5	20.0%
Participant B1						
1	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant B2						
1	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	0/10	0.0%	1/5	20.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant C1						
1	1/5	20.0%	5/10	50.0%	0/5	0.0%
2	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	3/5	60.0%
3	0/5	0.0%	3/10	30.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant C2						
1	1/5	20.0%	1/10	10.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
Participant D1						
1	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	0/10	0.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant E1						
1	0/5	0.0%	1/10	10.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	0/5	0.0%	0/10	0.0%	1/5	20.0%

Data chart 4

These data charts represent the testing on day 28 of the experiment, during which each contestant shot the same number of shots as on day 1.

Raw data of test day 3 (Day 35 Week 5, 25th February, 2024):

C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Number of test:	Left Elbow (5 shots)	In (%) Left Elbow	Free Throw (10)	In (%) Free throw	Right Elbow (5 shots)	In (%) Right Elbow
Participant A1						
1	2/5	40.0%	6/10	60.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	4/5	80.0%	5/10	50.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	5/10	50.0%	4/5	80.0%
Participant A2						
1	2/5	40.0%	7/10	70.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	3/5	60.0%	5/10	50.0%	4/5	80.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	4/10	40.0%	3/5	60.0%
Participant A3						
1	2/5	40.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	3/5	60.0%	7/10	70.0%	4/5	80.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	5/10	50.0%	3/5	60.0%
Participant B1						
1	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	6/10	60.0%	3/5	60.0%
3	3/5	60.0%	7/10	70.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant B2						
1	2/5	40.0%	5/10	50.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	5/10	50.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	3/5	60.0%	2/10	20.0%	4/5	80.0%
Participant C1						
1	3/5	60.0%	7/10	70.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	6/10	60.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	5/10	50.0%	4/5	80.0%
Participant C2						
1	2/5	40.0%	7/10	70.0%	3/5	60.0%
2	3/5	60.0%	5/10	50.0%	3/5	60.0%
3	5/5	100.0%	6/10	60.0%	4/5	80.0%
Participant D1						
1	1/5	20.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	3/10	30.0%	1/5	20.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant E1						
1	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	1/10	10.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%

Data chart 5

Number of test:	3pt Right Wing (5 shots)	In (%) 3pt Right Wing	3pt Top of the key (10 shots)	In (%) 3pt Top of the	3pt Left Wing (5 shots)	In (%) 3pt Left Wing
Participant A1						
1	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant A2						
1	2/5	40.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	3/5	60.0%	3/10	30.0%	1/5	20.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	4/10	40.0%	4/5	80.0%
Participant A3						
1	3/5	60.0%	1/10	10.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	3/10	30.0%	0/5	0.0%
Participant B1						
1	4/5	80.0%	3/10	30.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant B2						
1	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
Participant C1						
1	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	4/5	80.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	2/10	20.0%	2/5	40.0%
Participant C2						
1	3/5	60.0%	4/10	40.0%	2/5	40.0%
2	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	3/5	60.0%
3	2/5	40.0%	5/10	50.0%	1/5	20.0%
Participant D1						
1	0/5	0.0%	4/10	40.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	1/5	20.0%	3/10	30.0%	0/5	0.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	2/10	20.0%	1/5	20.0%
Participant E1						
1	2/5	40.0%	3/10	30.0%	1/5	20.0%
2	0/5	0.0%	2/10	20.0%	2/5	40.0%
3	1/5	20.0%	1/10	10.0%	0/5	0.0%

Data chart 6

These data charts represent the testing on day 35 of the experiment, during which each contestant shot the same number of shots as on the previous testing days.

Appendix E Raw data from HomeCourt of participants:

Raw data from HomeCourt Participant A1:

	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2 Point Shots Made	1	56	1.4	133	7
	2	58	1.1	131	12
	3	57	1.4	135	11
	4	56	1.1	136	14
	5	55	1.4	140	12
	6	57	1.4	137	14
	7	55	1.4	141	7
	8	59		130	8
	9	60	1.4	133	7
	10	55	1.4		9
	11	58	1.4	141	7
	12	56	1.0	134	9
	13	56	1.4		
	14	60	1.4	133	7
	15	52	1.4	132	13
	16	52	1.4	131	12
	17	51	1.4	141	8
	18	59	1.3	131	11
	19	58	1.4	132	7
	20	59	1.4	136	12
	21	60	1.0	141	16
	22	58	1.4	130	
	23	55	1.4	141	13
2 Point Shots Missed	24	50	1.2	120	8
	25	62	1.4	128	7
	26	53	1.3	137	7
	27	51	1.1	124	11
	28			132	10
	29	48	1.4	121	10
	30	65	1.4	125	13
	31	48	1.4	121	14
	32	62	1.5	138	8
	33	53	1.5	125	11
	34	63	1.3	128	8
	35	68	1.6	139	7
	36	52	1.2	136	
	37	59	1.3	121	9
	38	60	1.6	124	9
	39	59	1.6	135	11
	40	52	1.5		13
	41			126	
	42	56	1.6	139	13
	43	65	1.5	134	8
	44	62	1.6	133	12
	45	53	1.1	134	8
	46	65	1.6	137	14
	47	55	1.1	127	11
	48	66	1.4	129	8
	49	59	1.0	125	14
	50	66	1.6	125	12
	51	62		139	
	52	63	1.4	137	8
	53	58	1.3	132	
	54	68	1.0	125	7
	55	61	1.5		8
	56	56	1.3	122	9
	57	60	1.5	130	9
	58	48	1.6	127	10
	59	53	1.6	136	8
	60		1.6	129	11

Data chart 1 of participant A1

	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
3 Point Shots Made	1	59	1.0	131	11
	2	56	1.0	130	11
	3	60	1.0	126	12
	4	67	1.1		13
3 Point Shots Missed	5	60	1.0	120	6
	6	51	1.5	122	8
	7	56	1.5	122	8
	8		1.5	125	8
	9	59	1.5	117	8
	10	54	1.5	114	8
	11	57		119	6
	12	52	1.0	130	6
	13	51	1.3		6
	14	56	1.1	129	6
	15	54	1.1	122	6
	16	61	1.0	121	
	17	59	1.5	129	8
	18	59	1.0	121	6
	19	61		126	8
	20	50	1.1	119	6
	21	56	1.0	129	6
	22	57	1.0	125	6
	23	62	1.5	125	6
	24	53	1.2	118	6
	25	52	1.3	126	6
	26	51	1.4	124	6
	27	49	1.5	116	8
	28	61	1.5	115	8
	29	58	1.2	127	6
	30	59	1.1	130	6
	31	53	1.0	121	6
	32	57	1.2	123	6
	33	50	1.2	128	6
	34	56	1.3	121	6
	35	62	1.5	130	8
	36	61	1.5	123	8
	37	54	1.2	127	6
	38	62	1.3	129	6
	39	52	1.1	127	6
	40	62	1.5	115	8
	41	61	1.0	124	6
	42	60	1.5	119	8
	43	57	1.5	113	8
	44	61	1.5	120	8
	45	53	1.2	117	6
	46	60	1.3	128	6
	47	57	1.4	112	6
	48	49	1.2	130	6
	49	54	1.3	119	6
	50	51	1.1	119	6
	51	62	1.3	112	6
	52	55	1.0	115	6
	53	56	1.5	119	8
	54	58	1.0	129	6
	55	54	1.4	114	6
	56	51	1.2	130	6
	57	60	1.4	128	6
	58	52	1.5	120	8
	59	56	1.5	118	6
	60	52	1.0	116	6

Data chart 2 of participant A1

Day 35	Day35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2 Point Shots Made	1	53	1.1	116	8
	2	48	1.0	120	8
	3	55	1.2	116	8
	4	46	1.0	118	8
	5		1.1	116	9
	6	55	1.1	118	8
	7	51			9
	8	49	1.0	119	8
	9	50	1.1	118	8
	10	55	1.2	119	9
	11	50	1.1	117	9
	12	56	1.1	118	8
	13	46	1.2	117	8
	14	52	1.1	119	8
	15	56	1.0	117	
	16		1.2		8
	17	55	1.1	116	8
	18	52	1.1	119	8
	19	48	1.0	116	9
	20	51	1.1	118	9
	21	54	1.1	116	8
	22	47	1.0	120	
	23	54	1.1	118	9
	24	52	1.1		8
	25	50	1.2	115	9
	26		1.2	120	8
	27	45	1.2	117	9
	28	53	1.1	119	8
	29	57	1.1	115	9
	30	48	1.1	119	9
2 Point Shots Missed	31	50	0.8	120	9
	32	49	0.7	121	8
	33	51	0.8		
	34	52	1.0	123	8
	35	50	0.8	118	7
	36	48	0.9	120	9
	37	53	0.7	125	9
	38	49	0.9	116	10
	39	52	0.8	124	8
	40	53	0.9	116	7
	41	48	0.8	122	9
	42	51	0.9	117	10
	43	50	0.8	118	9
	44	51	0.7	125	7
	45	53	0.7	117	9
	46	49	0.8	124	8
	47	50	0.9	120	8
	48	52	0.6	123	10
	49	53	0.9	121	9
	50	49	0.8	120	7
	51			126	9
	52	48	0.7	118	8
	53	51	1.0	122	8
	54	52	0.8	115	9
	55	50	0.8	123	8
	56	48	0.9	119	8
	57	51	0.7	126	9
	58	53	0.9	117	9
	59	48	0.7	123	8
	60	51	0.9	118	9

Data chart 3 of participant A1

	Day35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
3 Point Shots Made	1	47	1.1	119	9
	2	49	0.9	111	11
	3		0.9	122	11
	4	49	1.2	121	12
	5	48	1.0	117	9
	6	46	1.0	115	10
	7	50	0.9	122	10
	8	46	1.1	116	13
	9	48	1.1	114	8
	10	48	1.1	112	12
	11	44	1.1		10
	12	50	1.0	117	13
	13		0.9	123	9
	14	47	1.1	111	10
	15	48	1.1	119	12
	16	49	1.2	112	8
	17	49	0.9	117	12
	18	46	1.0	116	10
	19	46	1.1	113	11
	20	50	1.1	120	12
	21	47	1.0		9
	22		1.0	118	11
	23	48	1.0	122	9
3 Point Shots Missed	24	49	1.2	124	
	25	47	1.3	125	8
	26	51	1.3	123	9
	27	48	1.1	128	7
	28	46	1.2	120	10
	29	52	1.0	122	7
	30			126	8
	31	51	1.3	130	10
	32	45	1.1	120	8
	33	48	1.2	128	9
	34		1.2	124	7
	35	49	1.1	130	10
	36	45	1.1	127	8
	37	53	1.2	123	8
	38	47	1.0	129	9
	39	50	1.1		8
	40	49	1.3	125	9
	41	53	1.1	121	9
	42	44	1.3	128	8
	43	51	1.2	122	8
	44	46	1.1	128	9
	45	52	1.1	126	7
	46	43	1.2	121	9
	47	53	1.3	120	10
	48		1.1	124	7
	49	46	1.3	125	8
	50	54	1.1	123	9
	51	43	1.1		
	52	52	1.3	126	9
	53			120	
	54	53	1.3	125	7
	55	50	1.2	129	9
	56	47	1.2	121	9
	57			127	8
	58	45	1.1	118	8
	59	51	1.2	130	10
	60	48	1.3	124	7

Data chart 4 of participant A1

Raw data from HomeCourt Participant A2:

Participant A2		Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2 Point Shots Made	1	52	1.6	112	5
	2		1.3	114	2
	3	54	1.6	106	4
	4	52	1.8	108	4
	5	57	1.4	113	4
	6	52	1.6		5
	7	54	1.3	111	2
	8	58	1.5	107	5
	9	55	1.4	105	
	10	57	1.3	114	
	11	58	1.5	105	3
	12			109	5
	13	56	1.4	111	2
	14	58	1.6	117	4
	15	58	1.8	105	4
	16	54	1.4	109	5
	17	51	1.8	105	2
	18	52	1.8	108	3
	19	51	1.1	112	3
	20	53	1.3	107	4
	21	51	1.5	106	5
	22	55	1.2	105	4
	23	53	1.4	112	2
	24	57	1.7	114	5
	25	58	1.7	113	5
2 Point Shots Missed	26	53	1.9	111	3
	27	58	1.3	114	2
	28	53	1.4	102	2
	29	58	1.8	102	3
	30	57	1.1	107	1
	31	58	1.7	110	4
	32	58	1.6	112	3
	33	49	1.4	114	3
	34	49	1.3	114	2
	35	51	1.6	104	1
	36	58	1.5	104	2
	37	50	1.6	102	2
	38	49	1.4	109	2
	39	57	1.9	109	1
	40	52	1.2	112	3
	41	58	1.2	102	1
	42	49	1.4	106	3
	43	55	1.7	107	3
	44		1.8	102	3
	45	49	1.5	102	4
	46	55	1.9	112	1
	47	50	1.4	102	4
	48	49	1.9	105	1
	49	49	1.8	102	2
	50	49	1.9	105	2
	51	58	1.9	114	2
	52	56	1.9	104	2
	53	57	1.9	112	1
	54	55	1.8	102	1
	55	53			2
	56	50	1.2	104	4
	57	59	1.1	104	2
	58	51	1.3	109	1
	59	52	1.5	103	1
	60	51	1.6	110	1

Data chart 1 of participant A2

Participant A2		Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
3 Point Shots Made	1	57	1.6	111	9
	2	57	1.6	110	9
	3	51	1.6	111	9
	4	53	1.6	116	10
	5	52	1.6	109	10
	6	51	1.6	110	10
	7	57	1.6	109	12
	8	51		115	12
	9	57	1.6	112	9
	10	51	1.5	111	11
	11	57	1.6		
	12	55	1.4	111	10
	13	53	1.6	115	9
	14	53	1.5	116	9
	15	57	1.6	110	10
	3 Point Shots Missed	16	53	1.6	118
17		48	1.7	102	7
18		55	1.8	108	13
19		53	1.4	107	6
20		48	1.8	105	12
21		55	1.8	107	13
22		51	1.6	103	12
23		56	1.9	98	9
24		48	2.0	98	4
25		51	1.6	104	9
26		49	1.9	99	8
27		49	1.9	99	6
28			2.1	110	8
29		55	2.0	108	7
30		54	2.1	100	5
31		53	1.8	98	8
32		51	1.6	109	6
33		55	2.1	101	9
34		51	1.5	100	4
35		55	1.8	106	13
36		54	1.5	99	12
37		48	2.1	101	
38		54		110	12
39		48	2.0	106	13
40		49	1.7	104	5
41		48	1.6	103	10
42		51	1.6	107	13
43		53	1.5	100	13
44		48	1.8	110	10
45		51	1.5	108	5
46		55	1.7	105	
47		48	1.9	99	4
48		53	2.0	106	6
49		52	1.4	109	13
50		48	1.8	104	7
51		51	1.9	102	10
52		53	2.1	99	7
53		48	1.8	107	13
54		55		109	11
55		51	1.6	99	7
56		48	1.4		12
57		48	1.8	98	5
58		55	1.6	110	8
59		52	2.1	105	6
60		48	1.6	105	11

Data chart 2 of participant A2

	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
2 Point Shots Made	1	48	1.0	117	8	
	2	47	1.0	116	8	
	3	48	1.0	117	9	
	4	48	1.0	116	8	
	5			0.9	117	8
	6	46	1.1	119	8	
	7	49	1.1	116	8	
	8	49	1.1	119	8	
	9	47	0.9	118	8	
	10	46	1.1	116	7	
	11	49	1.1	116	9	
	12	49	1.0	118	8	
	13		1.1	119	8	
	14	48	0.9	119	8	
	15	49	1.0	115	8	
	16	47	1.1		8	
	17	48	1.1	120	8	
	18	49	1.0	118	7	
	19	48	1.1	119	9	
	20	49	1.0	115	8	
	21	49	1.0	120	8	
	22	48	1.1	117	8	
	23	48	1.0	117		
	24	47	1.1	117	8	
	25	49		118	8	
	26	47	1.1	118	7	
	27	48	1.0	117	8	
	28	47	1.1	119	8	
	29	48	0.9	116	8	
	30	48	1.1	120	8	
	31	47	1.0	116	8	
2 Point Shots Missed	32	51	0.8			
	33	50	0.8	122	8	
	34	51	0.9	123	9	
	35	52	0.9	121	8	
	36	51	0.9	123	8	
	37	50	0.8	119	8	
	38	52	0.8	126	8	
	39	51	0.9	120	8	
	40	52	0.8	119	8	
	41	50	0.9	121	7	
	42	52	0.9	123	9	
	43		0.8	120	8	
	44	51	0.9	124	8	
	45	49	0.9	123	8	
	46	53	0.9	120	8	
	47	51	0.8		8	
	48	52	0.9	124	8	
	49	52	1.0	123	7	
	50	50	0.9	124	9	
	51	51	0.8	125	8	
	52	51		121	8	
	53	53	0.9	120	8	
	54	52	0.9	121	8	
	55	52	0.8	121		
	56	51	0.9	123	8	
	57	51	0.8	122	8	
	58	50	0.8	123	9	
	59	52	0.9	125	8	
	60	51	0.9	120	9	

Data chart 3 of participant A2

	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
3 Point Shots Made	1	48	1.0	120	8
	2	48	1.0	122	8
	3	50	1.0	123	9
	4	48	1.0	121	8
	5	47	0.9	123	8
	6	47	1.1	119	8
	7	49	1.1	122	8
	8	48	1.1	120	8
	9	49		119	8
	10	47	1.1	121	7
	11	49	1.1	123	9
	12	49	1.0	120	8
	13	48	1.1	124	8
	14	46	0.9	123	
	15	50	1.0	120	8
	16	48	1.1	122	8
	17	49	1.1	124	8
	18	49	1.0	123	7
	19	47	1.1	124	9
	20	48	1.0	125	8
	21	48	1.0	121	8
	22	50	1.1	120	8
	23	49	1.0	121	8
	24	49	1.1	121	8
	25	48	1.0	119	8
3 Point Shots Missed	26	55			8
	27	54	1.2	122	8
	28	55	1.1	123	9
	29	54	1.1	121	8
	30	56	1.3	123	8
	31	54	1.1	124	8
	32	55	1.2	126	8
	33	55	1.1	126	8
	34	56	0.9	127	8
	35	54	1.3	126	7
	36	55	1.1	129	9
	37	56	1.0	130	8
	38	54	1.1	128	8
	39	55	0.9	129	8
	40	56	1.0	127	8
	41	55	1.3	129	8
	42	54	1.1	130	8
	43	56	1.2	128	7
	44	55	1.0	129	9
	45	55	1.0		8
	46	56	1.1	127	8
	47		1.3	129	8
	48	55	1.0	129	8
	49	55	1.2	128	8
	50	56	1.0	129	8
	51	54	1.1	127	8
	52	56	1.2	129	8
	53	54	1.2	129	8
	54			128	8
	55	56	1.1	128	8
	56	55	1.2	130	8
	57	55	1.1	128	8
	58	54	1.0	128	8
	59	55	1.2	127	8
	60	55	1.1	128	8

Data chart 4 of participant A2

Raw data from HomeCourt Participant A3:

A	B	C	D	E	F
Participant A3		Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2 Point Shots Made	1	70	1.1	119	6
	2	67	1.0	120	6
	3	68	1.4	116	5
	4	70	1.3	116	6
	5	64	1.4	117	5
	6	63	1.0	117	6
	7	60	1.0	113	6
	8	61	1.3	118	6
	9	62	1.0	113	5
	10	61	1.0	120	6
	11	68	1.1	113	6
	12	65	1.4	118	6
	13	67	1.2	115	6
	14	69	0.9	114	6
	15				6
	16	63	1.3	120	6
	17	67	1.2	114	6
	18	63	1.2	120	5
	19	60	1.0	120	6
	20	64	1.4	120	5
	21	70	1.2	113	5
	22	64	1.3	120	5
	23	63			6
	24	71	1.2	120	5
	25	67	1.4	118	6
2 Point Shots Missed	26	63	1.1	120	10
	27	62	1.6	120	9
	28	63	1.4	120	10
	29	63	0.8	120	9
	30	64	0.8	120	11
	31	63	0.9	120	9
	32	63	1.0	120	11
	33	60	1.5	120	10
	34			120	8
	35	63	1.1	120	8
	36	64	1.4	120	11
	37	60	1.7	120	9
	38	62	1.4	120	9
	39	61	1.3	120	9
	40	61	0.8	120	11
	41	64	1.0	120	10
	42	63	1.6	120	10
	43	62	1.6	120	10
	44	60	1.8	120	9
	45	64	1.4	120	10
	46	64	1.2	120	10
	47	61	1.3	120	9
	48	60	1.2	120	10
	49	63	1.4	120	9
	50	64	1.3	120	11
	51	64	1.5	120	10
	52	63	1.6	120	10
	53	62	1.3	120	11
	54	62	1.3	120	10
	55	64	1.7	120	11
	56	63	1.5	120	11
	57			120	11
	58	61	1.5	120	11
	59	61	1.7	120	9
	60	61	1.5	120	10

Data chart 1 of participant A3

Participant A3		Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
3 Point Shots Made	1	50	1.4	122	10	
	2	58	1.3	118	8	
	3	56	1.3	113	9	
	4	54	1.2	109	11	
	5	56	1.4	124	12	
3 Point Shots Missed	6	50	1.8	108	8	
	7	54	1.6	114	9	
	8	53	1.5	112	10	
	9	54	1.5	110	11	
	10	53	1.6	114	10	
	11	54	1.6	113	9	
	12	55	1.7	117	8	
	13	50	1.4	116	8	
	14	55	1.5	115	9	
	15	56	1.6	119	11	
	16				114	9
	17	55	1.7	117	10	
	18	53	1.5	118	10	
	19	54	1.7	120	8	
	20	55	1.7	113	9	
	21	54	1.5	116	10	
	22	53	1.7	118	10	
	23	51	1.7	108	11	
	24	54	1.5	119	9	
	25	53	1.7	113	8	
	26	54	1.5	117	11	
	27	54	1.6	114	9	
	28	55	1.5	118	11	
	29	55	1.6	118	11	
	30	55	1.5	110	11	
	31	55	1.6	117	9	
	32	52	1.5	120	11	
	33	54	1.6	111	11	
	34	53	1.5	119	10	
	35	55	1.5	117	9	
	36				120	8
	37	54	1.5	111	10	
	38	55	1.7	110	11	
	39	55				9
	40	52	1.7	111	9	
	41	53	1.6	119	9	
	42	53	1.5	118	8	
	43	53	1.7	117	8	
	44	53	1.6	110	9	
	45	54	1.8	120	9	
	46	54	1.7	120	10	
	47	54	1.6	115	9	
	48	54	1.7	117	11	
	49	52	1.6	115	11	
	50		1.7	112	8	
	51	55				11
	52	55	1.5	112	8	
	53	56	1.7	110	10	
	54	53	1.6	120	9	
	55	52	1.5	120	9	
	56	55	1.6	114	11	
	57	53	1.6	113	10	
	58	53	1.6			
	59	54	1.5	111	11	
	60	55	1.6	116	11	

Data chart 2 of participant A3

	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
2 Point Shots Made	1	55	0.76	116	6	
	2	56	1.21	116	8	
	3	58	0.91	117	9	
	4	55	0.79	116	8	
	5	57	1.34	117	8	
	6	55	0.88	119	8	
	7	57	1.02	116	8	
	8	57	1.05	119	8	
	9				118	8
	10	56	1.27	116	7	
	11	57	1.1	116	9	
	12	58	1.03	118	8	
	13	55	0.91	119	8	
	14	56	0.93	119	8	
	15	57	1.02	115	8	
	16	55	1.26	119	8	
	17		1.12	120	8	
	18	58		118	7	
	19	55	0.98	119	9	
	20	58	1.01	115	8	
	21	58	1.1	120	8	
	22		1.26		8	
	23	58	0.96	117	8	
	24	55	1.17	117	8	
	25	58	0.95	118	8	
	26	57	0.89	118	8	
	27	58	1.22	117	8	
	28		0.88	119	8	
	29	56	1.1	116	8	
	30	58	1.11	120	8	
	31	57	1.2	115	8	
2 Point Shots Missed	32	54	1.05	120	8	
	33	55	0.88	117	9	
	34	54	1.46	116	10	
	35	54	1.1	116	8	
	36			122	9	
	37	55	0.6	116	8	
	38	53	1.28	117	10	
	39	57	1.28	119	8	
	40	58	1.28	124	8	
	41	52	1.65	116	9	
	42	56	1.36	124	8	
	43	53	0.99	116	10	
	44	54	1.08	125	8	
	45	57	1.37	120	10	
	46	49	0.65	125	8	
	47	49	1.34	121	10	
	48	48	1.34	123	10	
	49	56	0.82	115	8	
	50	56	0.73	118	9	
	51	57	0.94	116	9	
	52	58	0.99	118	9	
	53	56	1.23	116	8	
	54	53	1.08	118	10	
	55	56	1.71	119	9	
	56	49	0.7	115	10	
	57	55			10	
	58	50	0.76	121	8	
	59	58	1.32	118	10	
	60	53	0.87	120	9	

Data chart 3 of participant A3

	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
3 Point Shots Made	1	48	1.0	120	8
	2	48	1.0	122	8
	3	50	1.0	123	9
	4	48	1.0	121	8
	5	47	0.9	123	8
	6	47	1.1	119	8
	7	49	1.1	122	8
	8	48	1.1	120	8
	9	49		119	8
	10	47	1.1	121	7
	11	49	1.1	123	9
	12	49	1.0	120	8
	13	48	1.1	124	8
	14	46	0.9	123	
	15	50	1.0	120	8
	16	48	1.1	122	8
	17	49	1.1	124	8
	18	49	1.0	123	7
	19	47	1.1	124	9
	20	48	1.0	125	8
	21	48	1.0	121	8
	22	50	1.1	120	8
	23	49	1.0	121	8
	24	49	1.1	121	8
	25	48	1.0	119	8
3 Point Shots Missed	26	55			8
	27	54	1.2	122	8
	28	55	1.1	123	9
	29	54	1.1	121	8
	30	56	1.3	123	8
	31	54	1.1	124	8
	32	55	1.2	126	8
	33	55	1.1	126	8
	34	56	0.9	127	8
	35	54	1.3	126	7
	36	55	1.1	129	9
	37	56	1.0	130	8
	38	54	1.1	128	8
	39	55	0.9	129	8
	40	56	1.0	127	8
	41	55	1.3	129	8
	42	54	1.1	130	8
	43	56	1.2	128	7
	44	55	1.0	129	9
	45	55	1.0		8
	46	56	1.1	127	8
	47		1.3	129	8
	48	55	1.0	129	8
	49	55	1.2	128	8
	50	56	1.0	129	8
	51	54	1.1	127	8
	52	56	1.2	129	8
	53	54	1.2	129	8
	54			128	8
	55	56	1.1	128	8
	56	55	1.2	130	8
	57	55	1.1	128	8
	58	54	1.0	128	8
	59	55	1.2	127	8
	60	55	1.1	128	8

Data chart 4 of participant A3

Raw data from HomeCourt Participant B1:

Participant B1 Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
2 Point Shots Made	1	59	0.5	103	5
	2	59	0.5	108	6
	3	63	0.4	112	5
	4	54	0.7	103	5
	5	54	0.2	106	6
	6	62	0.2	115	5
	7	61	0.2	112	5
	8	52	0.3	105	6
	9	58	0.5	104	5
	10	60	0.5	116	5
	11	55	0.3	106	6
	12	56	0.4	104	5
	13	58	0.4	117	5
	14				6
	15	60	0.6	103	5
	16	51	0.4	109	5
	17	56	0.6	108	7
	18	54	0.2	116	5
	19	58	0.4	103	6
	20	60	0.6	103	6
	21	51	0.2	103	5
	22	52	0.4	116	6
	23	59	0.5	108	6
	24	60	0.2	104	5
	25	58	0.6	111	6
	26	63			6
	27	57	0.7	104	6
	28	51	0.4	111	5
	29	59	0.3	107	5
2 Point Shots Missed	30	56	0.6	110	2
	31			108	2
	32	57	0.7	114	2
	33	58	0.7	107	2
	34	54	0.4	108	2
	35	53	0.5	111	2
	36	52	0.4	110	2
	37	52	0.6	109	1
	38				2
	39	60	0.6	109	1
	40	59	0.6	114	2
	41	52	0.5	107	2
	42	60	0.5	108	2
	43	53	0.5	113	2
	44	52	0.4	109	2
	45	52	0.9	108	2
	46	59	0.6	110	2
	47	60	0.6	111	2
	48	52	0.6	112	2
	49	57	0.6	109	2
	50	59	0.5	110	2
	51	55	0.7	109	2
	52	54	0.8	114	2
	53	52	0.5	112	1
	54	54	0.7	111	2
	55	55	0.7	110	2
	56	52	0.5	112	2
	57	58	0.7	109	2
	58	52	0.6	113	2
	59	59	0.6	110	1
	60	53	0.6	112	2

Data chart 1 of participant B1

	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
3 Point Shots Made	1	48	1.0	120	8	
	2	48	1.0	122	8	
	3	50	1.0	123	9	
	4	48	1.0	121	8	
	5	47	0.9	123	8	
	6	47	1.1	119	8	
	7	49	1.1	122	8	
	8	48	1.1	120	8	
	9	49		119	8	
	10	47	1.1	121	7	
	11	49	1.1	123	9	
	12	49	1.0	120	8	
	13	48	1.1	124	8	
	14	46	0.9	123		
	15	50	1.0	120	8	
	16	48	1.1	122	8	
	17	49	1.1	124	8	
	18	49	1.0	123	7	
	19	47	1.1	124	9	
	20	48	1.0	125	8	
	21	48	1.0	121	8	
	22	50	1.1	120	8	
	23	49	1.0	121	8	
	24	49	1.1	121	8	
	25	48	1.0	119	8	
3 Point Shots Missed	26	55			8	
	27	54	1.2	122	8	
	28	55	1.1	123	9	
	29	54	1.1	121	8	
	30	56	1.3	123	8	
	31	54	1.1	124	8	
	32	55	1.2	126	8	
	33	55	1.1	126	8	
	34	56	0.9	127	8	
	35	54	1.3	126	7	
	36	55	1.1	129	9	
	37	56	1.0	130	8	
	38	54	1.1	128	8	
	39	55	0.9	129	8	
	40	56	1.0	127	8	
	41	55	1.3	129	8	
	42	54	1.1	130	8	
	43	56	1.2	128	7	
	44	55	1.0	129	9	
	45	55	1.0		8	
	46	56	1.1	127	8	
	47			1.3	129	8
	48	55	1.0	129	8	
	49	55	1.2	128	8	
	50	56	1.0	129	8	
	51	54	1.1	127	8	
	52	56	1.2	129	8	
	53	54	1.2	129	8	
	54				128	8
	55	56	1.1	128	8	
	56	55	1.2	130	8	
	57	55	1.1	128	8	
	58	54	1.0	128	8	
	59	55	1.2	127	8	
	60	55	1.1	128	8	

Data chart 2 of participant B1

	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
2 Point Shots Made	1	48	1.0	117	8	
	2	47	1.0	116	8	
	3	48	1.0	117	9	
	4	48	1.0	116	8	
	5			0.9	117	8
	6	46	1.1	119	8	
	7	49	1.1	116	8	
	8	49	1.1	119	8	
	9	47	0.9	118	8	
	10	46	1.1	116	7	
	11	49	1.1	116	9	
	12	49	1.0	118	8	
	13			1.1	119	8
	14	48	0.9	119	8	
	15	49	1.0	115	8	
	16	47	1.1		8	
	17	48	1.1	120	8	
	18	49	1.0	118	7	
	19	48	1.1	119	9	
	20	49	1.0	115	8	
	21	49	1.0	120	8	
	22	48	1.1	117	8	
	23	48	1.0	117		
	24	47	1.1	117	8	
	25	49		118	8	
	26	47	1.1	118	7	
	27	48	1.0	117	8	
	28	47	1.1	119	8	
	29	48	0.9	116	8	
	30	48	1.1	120	8	
	31	47	1.0	116	8	
2 Point Shots Missed	32	51	0.8			
	33	50	0.8	122	8	
	34	51	0.9	123	9	
	35	52	0.9	121	8	
	36	51	0.9	123	8	
	37	50	0.8	119	8	
	38	52	0.8	126	8	
	39	51	0.9	120	8	
	40	52	0.8	119	8	
	41	50	0.9	121	7	
	42	52	0.9	123	9	
	43			0.8	120	8
	44	51	0.9	124	8	
	45	49	0.9	123	8	
	46	53	0.9	120	8	
	47	51	0.8		8	
	48	52	0.9	124	8	
	49	52	1.0	123	7	
	50	50	0.9	124	9	
	51	51	0.8	125	8	
	52	51		121	8	
	53	53	0.9	120	8	
	54	52	0.9	121	8	
	55	52	0.8	121		
	56	51	0.9	123	8	
	57	51	0.8	122	8	
	58	50	0.8	123	9	
	59	52	0.9	125	8	
	60	51	0.9	120	9	

Data chart 3 of participant B1

H	I	J	K	L	M	
	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
3 Point Shots Made	1	51	0.94	105	4	
	2	44	0.71	107	5	
	3	50	0.89	103	5	
	4	44	0.82	105	7	
	5	48	0.8	101	6	
	6	47	1.01	102	6	
	7	47	0.83	101	5	
	8	46	0.97	110	7	
	9	45	0.92	100	8	
	10	43	0.58	102	8	
	11	47	0.94	106	5	
	12	50	0.67	101	8	
	13	46	1.01	109	7	
	14	45	0.58	107	6	
	15	44	0.72	110	5	
	16	44	0.61	105	5	
	17	45	0.79	103	4	
	18	44	0.97	106	7	
	19	45	0.71	110	5	
	20	44	0.63	105	6	
	21	44	0.72	103	6	
	22	50	0.96	109	7	
	23	45	0.63	104	7	
3 Point Shots Missed	24			114	8	
	25	50	1.22	106	11	
	26	48	1.03	105	11	
	27	53	1.01	110	10	
	28	54	1.15	109	10	
	29	48	1	113	8	
	30	53	1.43	114	9	
	31	47	0.96	108	10	
	32	55	1.37	108	7	
	33	52	1.25	109	10	
	34	51	0.91	110	7	
	35	49	1.21	114	10	
	36	54	1.29	112	10	
	37	49	1.23	108	7	
	38	53	1.19	107	9	
	39	55	1.44	114	9	
	40	53	0.83	106	8	
	41	51	1.04	112	8	
	42				114	10
	43	51	1.12	111	9	
	44	50	1.18	109	11	
	45	48	1.3	107	11	
	46	50	1.32	108	11	
	47	50	1.01	112	7	
	48	48	1.17	111	11	
	49	50	1.15	114	8	
	50	49	0.95	113	9	
	51	51	1.36	113	10	
	52	47	1.38	114	8	
	53	54	1.27	107	9	
	54	53	1.21	108	8	
	55	51	0.9	108	7	
	56	54	1.07	110	7	
	57	54	1.15	111	8	
	58	48	1.25	107	7	
	59	52	0.91	105	9	
	60	55	0.95	109	10	

Data chart 4 of participant B1

Raw data from HomeCourt Participant B2:

Participant B2	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
2 Point Shots Made	1	57	1.3	132	2	
	2	54	1.1	125	2	
	3	50	1.3	132	3	
	4	51	1.1	125	2	
	5	50	1.2	124	3	
	6	51	1.2	129	3	
	7	54	1.2	127	1	
	8	56	1.1	132	1	
	9	56	1.1	135	1	
	10	52	1.1	134	3	
	11	54	1.1	135	2	
	12			135	1	
	13	52	1.4	133	2	
2 Point Shots Missed	14	60	1.0	129	6	
	15	55	0.8	138	4	
	16	58	1.0	139	4	
	17	57			5	
	18	59	1.0	136	6	
	19	58	1.0	138	4	
	20	57	0.8	129	4	
	21	60	1.0	142	4	
	22	54	0.8	134	6	
	23	54	0.8	142	4	
	24	57	1.0	129	5	
	25	61	1.0	134	6	
	26	56	0.8		6	
	27	55	0.9	126	4	
	28	61	0.9	130	6	
	29	55	1.0	133	6	
	30	57	0.9	133	5	
	31	60	1.0	142	6	
	32			137	4	
	33	56	0.9	133	6	
	34	57	1.0	142	4	
	35	61	1.0	137	5	
	36	61	0.7	131	5	
	37	54	0.8	138	4	
	38	55	0.9	135	5	
	39	61	0.8	142	5	
	40	59	0.9	142	6	
	41	59	0.9	132	4	
	42	61	1.0	136	5	
	43	54	0.9	130	6	
	44	54		137	6	
	45	61	1.0	142	6	
	46	61	0.9	141	5	
	47	60	0.7	132	5	
	48	55	0.8	127	4	
	49	58	1.0	142	5	
	50	61	1.0	133	6	
	51	61	0.8	131	5	
	52	54	0.8	131	6	
	53	60	1.0	134	4	
	54	54	0.8	142	4	
	55	61	0.9	142	5	
	56	57	0.8	131	4	
	57	61	0.8	132	6	
	58	57	0.9	135	4	
	59	56	1.0	126	5	
	60	56	0.9	129	6	

Data chart 1 of participant B2

Participant B2	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical		
3 Point Shots Made	1	55	1.2	131	6		
	2	53	1.4	133	6		
	3	56	1.6	132	5		
	4	53	1.3	133	7		
	5	53	1.2	130	6		
	6	53	1.4	135	7		
	7	54	1.6	127	5		
	8				129	7	
	9	53	1.6	134	5		
	10	53	1.1	129	5		
	11	53	1.1	133	6		
	12	55	1.4	129	8		
	13	55	1.5	127	6		
	14	54	1.6	129	6		
	15	53	1.3	135	6		
	16	53	1.2	130	6		
3 Point Shots Missed	17	66	1.2	123	8		
	18	64	1.4	130	7		
	19	64	1.3	121	9		
	20	61	1.4	123	9		
	21	65	1.4	130	8		
	22	60	1.4	130	8		
	23	60	1.0	128	9		
	24	60	1.1	119	9		
	25	57	1.4	127	9		
	26	66	1.3	128	8		
	27	57	1.4	123	8		
	28	56	1.3	130	9		
	29		1.4	130			
	30	65	1.4	128	8		
	31	64	1.1	120	8		
	32	59	1.4	130	9		
	33	54	1.4	130	7		
	34	67	1.1	122	8		
	35	55	1.4	130	7		
	36	65	1.2	130	8		
	37	64	1.3	123	7		
	38	66	1.3	128	8		
	39	64	1.1	123	7		
	40	58	1.1	119	9		
41	56	1.1	130	8			
42		1.2		7			
43	56	1.4	128	8			
44	63	1.1	120	8			
45	65	1.3	124	7			
46	62	1.4	130	9			
47	56	1.1	120	7			
48	54	1.2	118	7			
49	61	1.4	121	7			
50	60	1.4	122	9			
51	56	1.4	130	8			
52	58	1.1	129	7			
53	61	1.4	117	8			
54	62	1.1	117	9			
55	60	1.1	127	7			
56	67	1.4	129	8			
57	54	1.3	119	8			
58	62	1.2	128	8			
59	66	1.2	122	9			
60	57	1.2	123	8			

Data chart 2 of participant B2

	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical		
2 Point Shots Made	1	57	0.98	115	5		
	2	57	0.95	106	7		
	3	57	0.92	105	6		
	4	52	0.89	114	4		
	5	57	0.86	108	4		
	6	55	0.83	110	5		
	7	54	0.8	115	7		
	8				109	7	
	9	49	0.74	112	7		
	10	50	0.72	109	7		
	11	52	0.99	113	5		
	12	59	0.97	110	6		
	13	51	0.95	107	6		
	14	52				7	
	15	50	0.9	107	8		
	16	52	0.88	110	5		
	17	52	0.85	112	7		
	18	59	0.83	114	7		
	19	58	0.81	112	6		
	20				113	7	
	21	49	0.77	107	8		
	22	57	0.75	109	4		
	23	56	0.73	109	4		
	24	51	0.98	112	7		
	25	59	0.96	108	4		
	26	50	0.94	108	6		
2 Point Shots Missed	27	55	1.2	113	9		
	28	53	1.1	114	5		
	29	55	1.01	117	7		
	30	54	0.95	121	8		
	31	56	1.12	114	8		
	32	58	1.03	117	9		
	33	56	1.07	122	8		
	34				119	6	
	35	60	1.21	120	7		
	36	58	1.28	118	8		
	37	56	0.92	122	5		
	38	53	1.06	118	5		
	39	55	0.99	113	7		
	40	58	1.15	114	6		
	41	54	1.22	116	9		
	42				118		
	43	60	1.18	120	6		
	44	58	1.13	116	8		
	45	57	0.88	119	8		
	46	59	0.82	120	9		
	47	59	0.78	115	8		
	48	56	0.74	122	6		
	49	60	1	119	5		
	50			0.7		8	
	51	54	1.3	118	5		
	52	57	1.25	120	6		
	53	56	0.9	120	9		
	54	57	1	121	9		
	55	60	0.95	114	7		
	56	54	0.85	118	8		
	57	61	1.1	117	4		
	58	60	1.05	121	7		
	59	56	0.95	113	7		
	60	59	1.13	122	6		

Data chart 3 of participant B2

	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
3 Point Shots Made	1	48	1.0	120	8	
	2	48	1.0	122	8	
	3	50	1.0	123	9	
	4	48	1.0	121	8	
	5	47	0.9	123	8	
	6	47	1.1	119	8	
	7	49	1.1	122	8	
	8	48	1.1	120	8	
	9	49		119	8	
	10	47	1.1	121	7	
	11	49	1.1	123	9	
	12	49	1.0	120	8	
	13	48	1.1	124	8	
	14	46	0.9	123		
	15	50	1.0	120	8	
	16	48	1.1	122	8	
	17	49	1.1	124	8	
	18	49	1.0	123	7	
	19	47	1.1	124	9	
	20	48	1.0	125	8	
	21	48	1.0	121	8	
	22	50	1.1	120	8	
	23	49	1.0	121	8	
	24	49	1.1	121	8	
	25	48	1.0	119	8	
3 Point Shots Missed	26	55			8	
	27	54	1.2	122	8	
	28	55	1.1	123	9	
	29	54	1.1	121	8	
	30	56	1.3	123	8	
	31	54	1.1	124	8	
	32	55	1.2	126	8	
	33	55	1.1	126	8	
	34	56	0.9	127	8	
	35	54	1.3	126	7	
	36	55	1.1	129	9	
	37	56	1.0	130	8	
	38	54	1.1	128	8	
	39	55	0.9	129	8	
	40	56	1.0	127	8	
	41	55	1.3	129	8	
	42	54	1.1	130	8	
	43	56	1.2	128	7	
	44	55	1.0	129	9	
	45	55	1.0		8	
	46	56	1.1	127	8	
	47			1.3	129	8
	48	55	1.0	129	8	
	49	55	1.2	128	8	
	50	56	1.0	129	8	
	51	54	1.1	127	8	
	52	56	1.2	129	8	
	53	54	1.2	129	8	
	54				128	8
	55	56	1.1	128	8	
	56	55	1.2	130	8	
	57	55	1.1	128	8	
	58	54	1.0	128	8	
	59	55	1.2	127	8	
	60	55	1.1	128	8	

Data chart 4 of participant B2

Raw data from HomeCourt Participant C1:

Participant C1	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
2 Point Shots Made	1	62	1.7	119	3	
	2	59	1.8	120	2	
	3	58	2.7	120	3	
	4	60	1.8	121	3	
	5	62	2.8	110	2	
	6	59	1.3	120	2	
	7	58	1.2	105	3	
	8	57	1.1	119	3	
	9				119	3
	10	61	2.2	124	3	
	11	62	2.2	121	3	
	12	57	2.5	118	3	
	13	59	1.4	118	3	
	14	60	1.7	106	3	
	15		1.2		2	
	16	62	1.3	111	2	
	17	61	2.4	118	2	
	18	59	1.3	113	2	
	19	57	1.4		2	
	20	60	2.3	124	3	
	21	62	2.8	109	3	
	22	58	2.7	108	3	
	23	61	1.7	117	3	
	24	59	2.4	110	3	
	25	57	1.1	107	2	
2 Point Shots Missed	26	61	2.9	111	3	
	27	66	1.9	115	4	
	28	64	2.7	123	4	
	29	61	2.1	123	2	
	30	60	1.5	121	2	
	31	62	2.1	119	2	
	32	65	2.2	124	1	
	33	60	2.3	117	4	
	34	65	2.4	116	3	
	35	65	1.0	117	3	
	36	60	1.2	114	2	
	37	65	2.7	116	2	
	38	65	1.4	113	3	
	39	62	1.8	125	1	
	40	61			1	
	41	60	2.0	113	4	
	42	62	1.1	124	3	
	43	60	1.3	115	4	
	44	63	1.7	123	4	
	45			112	3	
	46	64	1.7	114	3	
	47	63	1.1	120	2	
	48	58	1.1	129	3	
	49	64	2.1	117	2	
	50	59	1.7	129	2	
	51	65	2.6	116	1	
	52	62	2.1	119	2	
	53	59	1.2	128	3	
	54	64	2.7	125	2	
	55	65	1.3	127	4	
	56	60	1.1	121	2	
	57	65	2.2	124	2	
	58	65	1.2	111	3	
	59	64	1.2	128	2	
	60	65	2.7	114	1	

Data chart 1 of participant C1

Participant C1	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
3 Point Shots Made	1	56	1.2	126	2	
	2	55	1.0	127	5	
	3	53	0.9	129	4	
	4	55	1.0	126	4	
	5	57	0.9	115	4	
	6	55	1.1	121	4	
	7	57	0.9	123	5	
	8	54		120	5	
	9				127	3
	10	54	1.1	123	4	
	11	59	1.1	119	3	
	12	59	1.0	129	4	
	13	56	1.4	119	5	
	14	56	1.3	121	3	
	15	57	0.9	123	3	
	16	55	0.8	126	4	
	17	59	1.0	124	5	
	18	59	1.3	122	4	
	19	54	0.9	117	5	
	20		0.8	128	3	
	21	55				4
	22	54	0.8	127	3	
	23	56	1.1	126	3	
	24	59	1.0	115	2	
	25	54	1.2	129	5	
	26	59	0.7	118	5	
3 Point Shots Missed	27	66	0.7	120	6	
	28	61	1.0	124	4	
	29	64	0.9	120	5	
	30	66	0.8	115	6	
	31	67	1.1	118	4	
	32	68	1.1	123	6	
	33	66	0.8	123	5	
	34	65	0.8	124	5	
	35	65	0.7	118	4	
	36	64	0.7	115	6	
	37	59	0.9	124	5	
	38	68	0.7	118	4	
	39	62	0.9	115	5	
	40	64	0.9	121	7	
	41	62	1.2	119	6	
	42	67	1.1	123	5	
	43			123	6	
	44	62	0.9	121	6	
	45	67	0.7	123	4	
	46	58	0.8	121	7	
	47	66	1.0	120	5	
	48	64	1.1	115	5	
	49	67	0.9	121	3	
	50	68	1.0	119	4	
	51	59	1.0	123	4	
	52	59			3	
	53	68	0.8	120	5	
	54	59	0.8	124	3	
	55	59	1.1	121	4	
	56	62	0.9	120	3	
	57	65	0.9	116	4	
	58	59	1.1	116	5	
	59	63	1.0	119	3	
	60	67	0.8	123	5	

Data chart 2 of participant C1

Day 35	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical		
2 Point Shots Made	1	61	1.2	118	3		
	2	61	0.83	119	3		
	3	61	1.13	116	1		
	4	61	0.88	115	3		
	5	57	1.11	116	2		
	6	59	0.94	112	2		
	7	60	0.98	117	2		
	8	59	1.09	120	3		
	9	61	0.68	113	4		
	10				114	4	
	11	60	1.05	116	2		
	12	58	1.03	117	3		
	13	59	0.92	116	2		
	14	60	1.24	120	2		
	15	60	0.78	115	3		
	16	60	1.2	114	3		
	17	60	0.73	113	2		
	18	59	1.17	119	2		
	19	60	0.66	117	2		
	20				118	2	
	21	60	0.99	116	2		
	22	61	1.03	117	3		
	23	60	1.29	113	3		
	24	59	0.9	118	2		
	25	61	1.2	119	2		
	26	60	1.09	115	3		
	27	60	0.95	112	1		
	28	61	1.07	116	3		
	29	61	1.25	120	3		
	30	60	0.71	117	4		
	31				1.23	120	4
	32	60	1.14	118	2		
2 Point Shots Missed	33	65			4		
	34	63	0.92	113	4		
	35	66	1.15	116	4		
	36	62	0.8	121	4		
	37	59	1.25	115	5		
	38	60	1.03	118	5		
	39	61	0.7	113	4		
	40	67	1.02	122	5		
	41	61	0.65	112	3		
	42				123	4	
	43	59	0.82	116	4		
	44	66	0.98	119	4		
	45	62	1.1	117	3		
	46	65	0.75	120	4		
	47	60	1.05	113	4		
	48	64	1.2	114	5		
	49	60	0.9	118	4		
	50	63	1.13	116	4		
	51	64	0.78	121	5		
	52	66	1.29	120	5		
	53	62	0.85	117	3		
	54	65	1.03	114	5		
	55	61	1.2	119	4		
	56	63	0.92	115	4		
	57	66	1.15	116	5		
	58	62	0.8	122	5		
	59	59	1.25	113	4		
	60	60	1.03	123	5		

Data chart 3 of participant C1

	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
3 Point Shots Made	1	48	1.0	120	8
	2	48	1.0	122	8
	3	50	1.0	123	9
	4	48	1.0	121	8
	5	47	0.9	123	8
	6	47	1.1	119	8
	7	49	1.1	122	8
	8	48	1.1	120	8
	9	49		119	8
	10	47	1.1	121	7
	11	49	1.1	123	9
	12	49	1.0	120	8
	13	48	1.1	124	8
	14	46	0.9	123	
	15	50	1.0	120	8
	16	48	1.1	122	8
	17	49	1.1	124	8
	18	49	1.0	123	7
	19	47	1.1	124	9
	20	48	1.0	125	8
	21	48	1.0	121	8
	22	50	1.1	120	8
	23	49	1.0	121	8
	24	49	1.1	121	8
	25	48	1.0	119	8
3 Point Shots Missed	26	55			8
	27	54	1.2	122	8
	28	55	1.1	123	9
	29	54	1.1	121	8
	30	56	1.3	123	8
	31	54	1.1	124	8
	32	55	1.2	126	8
	33	55	1.1	126	8
	34	56	0.9	127	8
	35	54	1.3	126	7
	36	55	1.1	129	9
	37	56	1.0	130	8
	38	54	1.1	128	8
	39	55	0.9	129	8
	40	56	1.0	127	8
	41	55	1.3	129	8
	42	54	1.1	130	8
	43	56	1.2	128	7
	44	55	1.0	129	9
	45	55	1.0		8
	46	56	1.1	127	8
	47		1.3	129	8
	48	55	1.0	129	8
	49	55	1.2	128	8
	50	56	1.0	129	8
	51	54	1.1	127	8
	52	56	1.2	129	8
	53	54	1.2	129	8
	54			128	8
	55	56	1.1	128	8
	56	55	1.2	130	8
	57	55	1.1	128	8
	58	54	1.0	128	8
	59	55	1.2	127	8
	60	55	1.1	128	8

Data chart 4 of participant C1

Participant C2	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
2 Point Shots Made	1	47	0.8	132	6	
	2	48	0.8	125	7	
	3	49	0.6	134	6	
	4	44	0.9	128	6	
	5	46	0.9	122	8	
	6		0.9		7	
	7	45	0.8	131	6	
	8	47	0.8	123	7	
	9	48	0.8	132	6	
	10			125	7	
	11	45	0.9	133	6	
	12	44	0.6	132	5	
	13	49	0.7	128	8	
	14	46	0.7	131	6	
	15	48	0.9	135	6	
	16	47	0.8	132	6	
	17	46	0.7	126	7	
	18	47	0.8	130	6	
	19	44	0.6	134	5	
	20			132		
	21	48	0.7	130	6	
	22	45	0.6	125	5	
	23	48	0.8	129	6	
	24	45	0.8	127	6	
2 Point Shots Missed	25	41	0.7	142	8	
	26	44	0.7	140	7	
	27	44	0.7	143	8	
	28	44	0.7	137	8	
	29	42	0.5	141	9	
	30	43	0.8	144	10	
	31	44	0.7	140	6	
	32	44	0.5	136	7	
	33			134	8	
	34	44	0.6	137	9	
	35	45	0.8	142	8	
	36	41	0.8	139	6	
	37	43	0.5	137	9	
	38	43	0.5	141	7	
	39	43	0.6	143	8	
	40	45	0.7	135	9	
	41	42	0.6	141	9	
	42			144	9	
	43	42	0.7	137	10	
	44	41	0.8	138	7	
	45	45	0.7	142	9	
	46	45	0.6	143	9	
	47	44	0.8	144	8	
	48	42	0.7	142	9	
	49	45	0.6	139	10	
	50	45	0.6	137	8	
	51	42	0.6	143	9	
	52	43	0.8	141	7	
	53	43	0.6	141	7	
	54	44	0.7	140	7	
	55	46	0.6	139	8	
	56	42	0.5	144	7	
	57	43	0.7	137	7	
	58	45	0.6	139	7	
	59	43	0.5	140	8	
	60	43	0.7	141	8	

Data chart 1 of participant C2

Participant C2	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
3 Point Shots Made	1	48	0.6	121	11	
	2	48	0.7	122	8	
	3	46	0.6	123	9	
	4	48	0.5	122	8	
	5	42	0.6	121	12	
	6	46	0.6	120	10	
	7	49	0.6	122	11	
	8	45	0.7	122	9	
	9	48	0.9	125	12	
	10	49	0.4	120	10	
	11	47	0.7	122	8	
	12	46	0.7	120	11	
	13	43	0.5	120	11	
3 Point Shots Missed	14	52	0.8	124	11	
	15	49	0.9	126	12	
	16	54	0.9	125	9	
	17				10	
	18	48	0.7	125	10	
	19	54	0.7	124	13	
	20	49	0.7	122	9	
	21	52	1.0	123	11	
	22	51	0.6	120	12	
	23	49	0.8	120	11	
	24	49	0.7	123	11	
	25	52	0.9	123	10	
	26	49	1.0	125	10	
	27	52	0.6	126	12	
	28	49	0.7	119	11	
	29	48	1.0	123	10	
	30	54	1.0	123	9	
	31	50	0.7	123	12	
	32	51	0.7	125	11	
	33		1.0	124	13	
	34	50	0.9	126	12	
	35	50	0.6	121	11	
	36	48	0.9	125	12	
	37	49	0.8	119	9	
	38	53		126	9	
	39	51	0.9	125	10	
	40	49	1.0	125	11	
	41	51			13	
	42	49	0.6	123	10	
	43	49	0.8	125	9	
	44	50	0.7	126	11	
	45	49	1.0	126	10	
	46	49	0.9	121	13	
	47		0.8	123	12	
	48	49	1.0	126	12	
	49	51	0.9	123	13	
	50	50	1.0	123	10	
	51	52	1.0	123	9	
	52	54	1.0	125	10	
	53	52		126	11	
	54	50	0.8	123	12	
	55	54	0.6	123	9	
	56	50	0.8	121	11	
	57	54	1.0	123	13	
	58	53	0.8	127	10	
	59	49	0.8	125	9	
	60	52	0.8	119	13	

Data chart 2 of participant C2

Day 35	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
2 Point Shots Made	1	50	0.8	126	7	
	2	45	0.65	125	7	
	3	52	0.75	133	8	
	4	44	0.9	121	7	
	5	48	0.7	130	7	
	6	49	0.95	123	7	
	7	42	0.85	134	8	
	8	51	0.75	128	7	
	9				127	7
	10	46	0.85	124	7	
	11	41	0.75	129	8	
	12	50	0.8	131	7	
	13	43	0.65	135	8	
	14	52	0.75	120	7	
	15	45	0.9	132	7	
	16					
	17	48	0.95	126	7	
	18	47	0.85	133	8	
	19	44	0.6	122	7	
	20	46	0.75	123	7	
	21	51	0.7	128	8	
	22	42	0.8	127	7	
	23	50	0.65	130	7	
	24	43	0.85	121	8	
	25	52	0.75	129	7	
	26	45	0.8	134	8	
	27	49	0.7	125	7	
	28	48	0.95	126	7	
	29	47	0.6	133	7	
	30	44	0.75	120	8	
	31	46	0.7	123	8	
	32	51	0.8	128	7	
	33				127	7
	34	50	0.85	130	8	
	35	43	0.75	121	7	
	36	52	0.9	135	8	
	37	49	0.9	132	7	
	38	48	0.6	128	7	
2 Point Shots Missed	39	46	0.7	130	8	
	40	44	0.6	131	8	
	41	47	0.8	129	7	
	42		0.85		8	
	43	43	0.75	129	8	
	44	48	0.9	131	8	
	45	49	0.7	130	8	
	46	46	0.65	132	8	
	47	47	0.8	129	8	
	48	45	0.75	131	8	
	49	48	0.85	129	8	
	50	50	0.7	130	7	
	51	44	0.6	132	8	
	52	46	0.8	131	8	
	53	45	0.75	129	8	
	54	43	0.9	132	8	
	55	49	0.7	130	8	
	56	47	0.65	129	8	
	57	44	0.8	131	7	
	58	46	0.75	130	8	
	59	48	0.85	132	8	
	60	50	0.7	129	8	

Data chart 3 of participant C2

Day 35	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical		
3 Point Shots Made	1	46	0.6	123	9		
	2	48	0.75	122	9		
	3	45	0.5	121	9		
	4	47	0.7	126	9		
	5	44	0.8	129	9		
	6	49	0.45	125	9		
	7	50	0.65	130	9		
	8	43				10	
	9			0.7	127	9	
	10	47	0.75	124	9		
	11	45	0.4	121	9		
	12	48	0.7	123	9		
	13	50	0.8	120	9		
	14	49	0.6	129	9		
	15	44	0.7	126	9		
	16	46	0.75	125	9		
	17					9	
	18	43	0.65	122	9		
	19	45	0.5	128	9		
	20	49	0.7	121	9		
	21	50	0.75	130	9		
	22	46	0.4	123	9		
	23	48	0.7	127	9		
	24	44	0.8	126	9		
	25	47	0.7	123	7		
3 Point Shots Missed	26	54	0.7	125	9		
	27	55	0.75	130	9		
	28	51	0.8	129	9		
	29	52	0.65	120	9		
	30	56	0.7	124	9		
	31	50	0.6	127	9		
	32	53	0.8	123	9		
	33	54	0.7	122	9		
	34	56	0.7	121	9		
	35	52	0.65	130	9		
	36	53	0.7	126	9		
	37	50	0.75	124	9		
	38	55	0.7	123	9		
	39	57	0.6	132	9		
	40	52	0.8	128	9		
	41	53	0.75	131	9		
	42				119	9	
	43	56	0.7	126	9		
	44	51	0.7	125	9		
	45	53	0.6	133	9		
	46	50	0.8	120	9		
	47	55	0.75	128	9		
	48	52	0.7	127	9		
	49	57	0.7	123	9		
	50	54	0.65	122	9		
	51	56	0.75	129	9		
	52	51	0.7	121	9		
	53	53	0.7	130	9		
	54		0.6	124	9		
	55	55	0.8	123	9		
	56	52			9		
	57	57	0.75	129	9		
	58	54	0.7	125	9		
	59	56	0.65	126	9		
	60	53	0.7	126	7		

Data chart 4 of participant C2

Raw data from HomeCourt Participant D1:

Participant D1 day 1		Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical		
2 Point Shots Made	1	54	2.2	128		3	
	2	53	2.2	133		1	
	3	52	2.2	130		2	
	4	53	1.9	132		2	
2 Point Shots Missed	5	42	2.2	165		2	
	6	42	2.0	162		2	
	7	40	2.0	172		2	
	8	38	2.0	176		2	
	9	40	1.9	178		2	
	10	40	1.9	161			
	11				172		2
	12	39	1.9	169			2
	13	39	2.0				2
	14	40	1.9	169			2
	15	40	1.9	177			2
	16	39	1.9	165			2
	17	39	1.9	154			2
	18	40	1.9	163			2
	19						
	20	41	2.1	174			2
	21	42	1.9	169			2
	22	39	1.9	165			2
	23	40	2.1	158			2
	24	38	1.9	162			2
	25	41	1.9	166			2
	26	41	1.9	153			2
	27	41	2.0	175			2
	28	40	2.1	174			2
	29	42	2.1	174			2
	30	38	1.9	161			2
	31	38	2.2	158			2
	32	39	1.9	158			2
	33	38	2.1	158			2
	34	38					2
	35	40	2.0	164			2
	36	39	1.9	167			2
	37	40	2.2	156			2
	38	42	1.9	154			2
	39	41	2.1	159			2
	40						
	41	38	1.9	168			2
	42	42	2.2	153			2
	43	42	2.1	156			2
	44	39	2.2	154			2
	45	40	1.9	152			2
	46	39	2.2	155			2
	47	41	2.2	168			2
	48	40	2.0	160			2
	49	41	2.2	162			2
	50	40	1.9	174			2
	51	38	1.9	165			2
	52	39	2.3	153			2
	53	41	2.2	167			2
	54	41	1.9	153			2
	55	40	2.2	155			2
	56	41	1.9	170			2
	57	40	2.3	166			2
	58				154		2
	59	40	2.2	158			2
	60	40	2.1	168			2

Data chart 1 of participant D1

Participant D1 day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
3 Point Shots Missed	1	44	1.8	141	5
	2	43	1.8	140	4
	3	42	1.8	141	4
	4	44	1.8	144	4
	5	42	1.7	142	3
	6	44	1.8	145	4
	7	43	1.8	141	4
	8	41	1.8	139	3
	9	44	1.7	141	5
	10	45	1.8	146	5
	11	42	1.8	147	4
	12	43	1.8	145	5
	13	40	1.7	138	3
	14	44	1.8	141	4
	15	43	1.8	145	4
	16	43	1.8	139	4
	17	45	1.7	142	3
	18				
	19	43	1.7	143	3
	20	42	1.7	141	3
	21	41	1.8	143	4
	22	42	1.8	142	4
	23	42			3
	24	42	1.8	141	4
	25	43	1.7	140	4
	26	44	1.7	142	3
	27	44	1.8	143	4
	28	40	1.7	139	4
	29	41	1.8	139	5
	30	43	1.7	142	4
	31	43	1.7	140	3
	32	42	1.8	143	5
	33	41	1.8	139	4
	34	43	1.7	140	3
	35				4
	36	42	1.8	140	3
	37	43	1.8	141	4
	38	42	1.7	139	3
	39	42	1.7	141	4
	40	42	1.8	142	3
	41	44	1.8	141	4
	42	40	1.7	139	5
	43	42	1.7	140	4
	44	44	1.7	142	5
	45	40	1.8	139	3
	46	42	1.7	141	4
	47	45	1.7	145	3
	48			138	4
	49	44	1.7	143	5
	50	40	1.7	139	3
	51	41	1.8	140	4
	52	44	1.7	144	5
	53	43	1.7	141	3
	54	43	1.8	141	3
	55	41	1.7	139	5
	56	44	1.7	143	4
	57	42	1.8	140	3
	58	41	1.7	139	5
	59	44	1.7	142	3
	60	41	1.8	140	4

Data chart 2 of participant D1

Day 35	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical		
2 Point Shots Made	1	51	0.9	118	5		
	2	49	1	128	4		
	3	47	1.2	120	6		
	4	43	0.8	119	3		
	5	46	1.1	130	5		
	6	54	1.25	118	6		
	7	44	1.3	123	4		
	8	52	0.75	126	3		
	9	55	0.6	125	4		
	10	45	1.2	119	5		
	11				130	6	
	12	48	1.05	121	4		
	13	56	0.85	119	5		
	14	50	0.95	129	6		
	15	42	1.3	124	3		
	16	57	1.1	127	4		
2 Point Shots Missed	17	44	0.8	121	6		
	18	47	0.95	123	4		
	19	50	1.1	116	7		
	20	49	1.05	114	5		
	21	52	1.2	113	6		
	22	48	1	112	3		
	23	45	0.9	117	5		
	24	46	0.7	118	7		
	25	57	1.3	115	6		
	26	56	0.75	120	4		
	27	47	1.25	122	5		
	28						
	29	49	1.15	119	5		
	30	51	1.1	111	7		
	31	54	0.7	114	6		
	32	52	1.3	117	5		
	33	55	0.8	116	4		
	34	47	1.2	121	6		
	35	42	0.95	113	5		
	36	48	1.05	122	4		
	37	43	0.9	125	7		
	38		0.75	112	6		
	39	51		120	5		
	40	44	1.15	118	4		
41	53	0.85	124	7			
42							
43	46	0.8	119	5			
44	47	0.7	111	4			
45	56	1.2	116	7			
46	49	0.95	117	6			
47	57	1.1	121	5			
48	48	1	115	4			
49	43	1.25	123	7			
50	50	0.9	120	6			
51	51	0.75	114	5			
52	45	1.2	122	4			
53	46	0.85	118	7			
54	47	0.8	116	6			
55				113	5		
56	49	0.95	124	4			
57	54	1.1	117	7			
58	48	1.2	115	6			
59	55	0.7	119	5			
60	56	1.25	121	4			

Data chart 3 of participant D1

Day 35	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
3 Point Shots Made	1	45	1.1	120	5
	2	48	0.9	117	6
	3	44	1	122	4
	4	47	1.25	119	7
	5	46	0.85	115	5
	6			123	4
	7	49	1.3	118	6
	8	50	1.2	121	5
	9	42	0.8	116	4
	10	48	1.1	120	7
	11	51	0.95	119	6
	12	47	1.15	123	4
	13	45	1.3	117	5
3 Point Shots Missed	14	42	0.9	120	5
	15	47	1.2	126	4
	16	48	0.95	118	5
	17	44	0.8	123	6
	18	49	1.1	124	7
	19	41	1.25	128	4
	20	43	0.85	119	6
	21	46	1.1	125	5
	22	45	1.3	121	4
	23	48	0.7	130	6
	24	41	1.2	120	5
	25	49	0.75	129	7
	26	43	1.05	117	4
	27	47	0.7	126	5
	28			123	6
	29	46	0.8	120	3
	30	45	0.75	128	7
	31	41	1.1	131	5
	32	43	0.7	122	6
	33	47	1.3	119	4
	34	48	0.85	124	5
	35	44	1.15		6
	36	49	0.8	120	3
	37	42	1.1		7
	38	46	1.25	129	4
	39	47	0.95	118	6
	40	44	1.2	130	5
	41	41		127	4
	42		1.3	123	6
	43	45	0.9	120	3
	44	49	1.05	128	7
	45	42	0.75	119	5
	46	46	1.2	122	6
	47	43	0.7	126	4
	48	47	1.1	121	7
	49	48	0.8	130	5
	50	44	1.15	117	4
	51	41	1.2	123	6
	52	49		124	3
	53	42	1.25	128	7
	54	47	0.85	120	4
	55	48	1.1	125	5
	56	44	0.95	131	6
	57	41	1.3	126	4
	58	46	0.7	119	5
	59	45	1.2	120	6
	60	45	1.1	122	7

Data chart 4 of participant D1

Raw data from HomeCourt Participant E1:

Participant E1	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
2 Point Shots Made	1	46	1.0		147	6
	2	47	3.2		160	6
	3	45	4.3		160	4
	4				150	5
	5	43	3.2		157	6
	6	49	1.1		145	2
2 Point Shots Missed	7	39	1.4		164	2
	8	37	1.1		167	2
	9	35	1.0		168	2
	10	36	1.7		170	2
	11	39	1.0		178	2
	12	38	1.0		161	2
	13				172	2
	14	36			169	2
	15	40	2.6		176	2
	16	34	3.3		169	2
	17	32	1.1		177	2
	18	38	2.6		165	2
	19	38	1.0		154	2
	20	37	2.6		163	2
	21	34	3.2		165	2
	22	34	1.4		174	2
	23	37	1.0		169	2
	24	34	1.0		165	2
	25	36	3.0		158	2
	26					2
	27	36	1.4		166	2
	28	34	1.1		153	2
	29	33	1.1		175	2
	30	38	2.4		174	2
	31	35	3.1		174	2
	32	34	1.9		161	2
	33	39				2
	34	35	1.0		158	2
	35	33	1.6		158	2
	36	38	2.1		164	2
	37	34	2.2		164	2
	38	37	2.4		167	2
	39	37	1.0		156	2
	40	40	2.9		154	2
	41	33	1.0		159	2
	42					2
	43	40	1.2		168	2
	44	38	1.7		153	2
	45	36	1.0		156	2
	46	38	3.0		154	2
	47	35	1.2		152	2
	48	35	1.0		155	2
	49	33	2.6		168	2
	50	36	3.2		160	2
	51	34	1.0		162	2
	52	37	1.6		174	2
	53	35	1.7		165	2
	54	39	2.6		153	2
	55	38	1.0		167	2
	56	33	2.7		153	2
	57	37	2.2		155	2
	58	38	1.0		170	2
	59	36	1.6		166	2
	60	33	1.0		154	2

Data chart 1 of participant E1

Participant E1	Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical	
3 Point Shots Made	1	41	3.0	150	5	
	2	42	3.0	156	4	
	3	41	3.0	151	3	
3 Point Shots Missed	4	46	3.9	153	3	
	5	36	2.3	157	6	
	6	42	4.4	155	3	
	7	39	3.2	142	2	
	8	31	1.3	152	1	
	9	38	3.1	150	2	
	10	31	3.1	148	2	
	11	47	1.0	160	5	
	12	44	3.8	154	1	
	13	37	1.0	146	1	
	14	35	1.2	151	2	
	15	38	2.6	143	2	
	16	36	1.8	155	5	
	17	37	2.8	148	5	
	18	47	4.4	145	4	
	19	38	1.0	144	2	
	20	44	3.2	142	2	
	21	33	3.5	156	4	
	22	40	1.0	155	5	
	23	39	1.0	151	3	
	24	41	1.6	147	3	
	25	43	1.4	149	6	
	26	46	2.0	158	4	
	27	35	1.0	144	4	
	28	37	1.9	142	1	
	29	31	3.5	145	1	
	30	42	3.8	151	2	
	31	47	2.8	142	4	
	32	38	1.0	143	1	
	33					1
	34	41	1.5	150	3	
	35				159	5
	36	40	1.0	159	5	
	37	42	4.2	147	5	
	38	42	1.0	149	5	
	39	42	2.1	159	4	
	40	34	1.0	152	3	
	41	34	3.8	148	2	
	42	35	1.0	157	4	
	43	44	3.1	159	4	
	44	39	1.0	154	1	
	45				146	4
	46	45	2.7	157	1	
	47	41	1.5	149	4	
	48				155	1
	49	38	2.0	151	1	
	50	40	1.3	159	1	
	51	33	1.0	143	6	
	52	45	3.0	144	4	
	53	47	2.4	145	2	
	54	45	1.0	146	1	
	55	45	1.0	146	4	
	56	45	1.0	144	1	
	57	34	1.9	155	5	
	58	47	1.0	145	3	
	59	42	1.0	146	5	
	60	38	3.1	145	3	

Data chart 2 of participant E1

Day 35	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2 Point Shots Made	1	46	0.9	122	6
	2	44	1.1	123	5
	3	48	0.95	120	4
	4	52	1	121	6
	5	43	0.8	119	3
	6				5
	7	45	0.75	118	4
	8	47	1.3	128	6
	9	49	0.7	124	5
	10	55	1.2	127	4
	11	41	0.85	126	6
	12	53	1.15	117	5
	13	50	1.3	118	7
2 Point Shots Missed	14	44	0.88	120	5
	15	48	1.18	126	5
	16	44			6
	17	46	1.23	128	8
	18	45	0.77	121	8
	19	44	1.07	122	5
	20	47	1.1	130	7
	21	48	1.21	121	6
	22	42	1.27	125	6
	23	48	0.8	121	7
	24				5
	25	49	1.11	121	6
	26	42	1.08	126	5
	27	43	0.89	127	4
	28	43	0.74	120	5
	29	48	1.17	122	6
	30	47	1.03	129	7
	31	46	1.25	120	5
	32	47	0.97	122	8
	33	49	1.01	123	5
	34	44	1.13	127	7
	35				6
	36	49	0.72	128	7
	37	47	1.3	135	6
	38	45	1.26	124	4
	39	46	1.05	129	7
	40	41	1.16	122	7
	41				5
	42	46	0.82	120	7
	43	48	1.15	123	4
	44	44	0.79	122	5
	45	44	1.24	120	4
	46	43	1.09	123	5
	47	46	0.73	120	6
	48	45	1.12	124	8
	49	43	1.02	134	7
	50	48	0.78	126	7
	51	47	0.9	122	6
	52	43	1.28	123	6
	53	48	1.2	121	6
	54	42	1.06	125	7
	55	47	0.75	121	7
	56	45	1.19	120	6
	57	44	0.95	124	5
	58	49	1.04	128	7
	59	46	0.81	120	6
	60	47	1.29	124	6

Data chart 3 of participant E1

Day 35	Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
3 Point Shots Made	1	43	0.87	115	5
	2	40	1.11	118	8
	3	43	0.95	120	6
	4		0.82	116	8
	5	41	1.03	122	5
	6	42	1.2	119	7
	7	41	0.91		6
	8	44	1.1	114	7
	9	42	0.88	112	8
	10	39	1.25	121	5
	11	45	1.05	111	6
	12	42	0.98	117	7
3 Point Shots Missed	13	43	1.12	123	8
	14	42	1.22	128	7
	15	43	0.94	124	6
	16	42	1.19	132	7
	17	43	0.98	128	6
	18	42	1.05	131	8
	19	43	0.88	122	6
	20	42	1.1	132	8
	21	42	1.23	121	9
	22	43	0.92	127	6
	23	42	1.15	131	9
	24	43	0.72	125	7
	25	43	1.19	133	8
	26	41	1.07	121	7
	27	42	1.27	132	7
	28	41	0.88	124	7
	29	41	1.24	120	8
	30	44	0.95	126	8
	31	44	1.1	128	6
	32	41	1.03	130	8
	33	44	1.26	128	9
	34	42	0.78	123	7
	35			129	7
	36	41	0.92	131	6
	37	43	1.2	125	9
	38	41	1.08	130	7
	39	42	1.15	122	7
	40	42	0.81	121	7
	41	44	1.22	126	9
	42	43	0.96	129	6
	43	44	1.3	128	9
	44	43	0.89	133	7
	45			124	7
	46	41	0.87	120	6
	47	44	1.19	131	9
	48	43	0.98	128	7
	49	44	1.14	122	7
	50	42	0.82	125	7
	51	43	1.26	126	9
	52	42	0.91	129	6
	53	43	1.18	130	9
	54	42	0.85	133	7
	55	44	1.21	124	7
	56	42	0.79	120	6
	57	44	1.25	131	9
	58	42	0.97	128	7
	59	44	1.15	122	7
	60	43	0.83	125	7

Data chart 4 of participant E1

Appendix G Graphs of participants Makes:

Participant A1

Participant A2

Participant A3

Participant B1

Participant B2

Participant C1

Participant C2

Participant D1

Participant E1

These graphs represent how each participant's percentage from each of the six areas increased or decreased during the 35-day period.

Appendix H Process data of shot-by-shot HomeCourt tracking:

Table. A1. Average Homecourt data for participant A1:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	57	1.3	135	10
2pts missed	58	1.4	130	10
3pts made	60	1	129	12
3pts missed	56	1.3	122	7
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	51	1.1	118	8
2pts missed	51	0.8	121	9
3pts made	48	1	117	11
3pts missed	49	1.2	125	8

Table. A2. Average Homecourt data for participant A2:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	55	1.5	110	4
2pts missed	53	1.6	107	2
3pts made	54	1.6	112	10
3pts missed	51	1.8	104	9
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	48	1	117	8
2pts missed	51	0.9	122	8
3pts made	48	1	122	8
3pts missed	55	1.1	127	8

Table. A3. Average Homecourt data for participant A3:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	65	1.2	117	6
2pts missed	62	1.3	120	10
3pts made	55	1.3	117	10
3pts missed	54	1.6	115	10
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	57	1	117	8
2pts missed	54	1.1	119	9
3pts made	49	0.9	109	6
3pts missed	52	1.2	114	9

Table. B1. Average Homecourt data for participant B1:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	57	0.4	108	6
2pts missed	55	0.6	110	2
3pts made	46	0.6	110	11
3pts missed	48	0.8	112	10
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	58	0.9175862069	109	7
2pts missed	54	1.1	115	9
3pts made	46	0.8	105	6
3pts missed	51	1.1	110	9

Table. B2. Average Homecourt data for participant B2:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	53	1.2	131	2
2pts missed	58	0.9	135	5
3pts made	54	1.4	131	6
3pts missed	61	1.3	125	8
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	54	0.9	110	6
2pts missed	57	1	118	7
3pts made	56	0.7	110	8
3pts missed	58	0.9	117	9

Table. C1. Average Homecourt data for participant C1:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	60	1.9	116	3
2pts missed	63	1.8	120	2
3pts made	56	1	123	4
3pts missed	64	0.9	120	5
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	60	1.015666667	116.4375	3
2pts missed	63	0.9903846154	117.2592593	4
3pts made	56	0.7526086957	112.375	6
3pts missed	62	0.8787878788	115.2058824	6

Table. C2. Average Homecourt data for participant C2:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	46	0.8	129	6
2pts missed	43	0.7	140	8
3pts made	46	0.6	121	10
3pts missed	51	0.8	124	11
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	47	0.8	128	7
2pts missed	46	0.8	130	8
3pts made	47	0.7	125	9
3pts missed	54	0.7	126	9

Table. D1. Average Homecourt data for participant D1:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	53	2.1	131	2
2pts missed	40	2	163	2
3pts made	0	0	0	0
3pts missed	43	1.8	141	4
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	49	1	124	5
2pts missed	49	1	118	5
3pts made	47	1.1	119	5
3pts missed	45	1	124	5

Table. E1. Average Homecourt data for participant E1:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	46	2.6	153	5
2pts missed	36	1.8	164	2
3pts made	41	3	152	4
3pts missed	40	2.1	150	3
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	48	1	122	5
2pts missed	46	1	124	6
3pts made	42	1	117	7
3pts missed	43	1	127	7

Table. Group D/E:

Day 1	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	49.5	2.4	142.0	3.5
2pts missed	38.0	1.9	163.5	2.0
3pts made	20.5	1.5	76.0	2.0
3pts missed	41.5	2.0	145.5	3.5
Day 35	Release angle	Release time	Leg angle	Vertical
2pts made	48.5	1.0	123.0	5.0
2pts missed	47.5	1.0	121.0	5.5
3pts made	44.5	1.1	118.0	6.0
3pts missed	44.0	1.0	125.5	6.0